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ANALYSIS OF THE FEASIBILITY OF INCLUDING LIBRAS IN THE INITIAL YEARS AND ITS INCLUSION IN ENEM

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ABSTRACT

Reality is imposed by the need to provide greater social inclusion and the challenge is to understand this paradigm that is presented in national education. The universe was made up of all Libras teachers and professionals. The population includes professionals and teachers who are in Faculties of Pedagogy and Faculties of Speech and Hearing Therapy, located in the city of Caldas Novas - GO.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: FROM TEACHING TO LEARNING, A PEDAGOGICAL REFLECTION

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is still seeking greater space in teaching and learning, even with the growing academic debate, there is still a need for ethical legitimization, this challenge will still depend on a development on the subject, through incentives and investments in technology. Given this scenario, what are the thoughts on artificial intelligence in teaching and learning? The general aim of this study was therefore to carry out a literature review on artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The research was bibliographical with a qualitative approach, seeking to bring a reflection on the subject. We found that artificial intelligence is advancing in the academic context, but that there are still difficulties in implementing it, due to ethical issues and technological development. We conclude that pedagogical reflection must be continuous, as AI is an essential tool.

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BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to present the Revista Brasileira de Produção Científica (Brazilian Journal of Scientific Production), an interdisciplinary electronic publication, from a historical perspective. Its aims and expectations will be described. In view of the need to disseminate scientific production from the various areas of knowledge, it was created with the aim of publicizing the scientific productions of teachers, students and professionals. The work is methodologically qualitative, with documentary and bibliographic methods.

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COMPARATIVE EDUCATION

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

Comparative education is a rich analytical tool for educational systems. It helps to sample similarities and differences, broadening the field of analysis and understanding of the national reality in relation to that of other countries, particularly in the field of public policies and educational management. This is basic research in nature and bibliographical in terms of research method. The aim of this study was to discuss the importance of comparative education and the comparative method in educational research, in the area of educational policy, as well as to disseminate and propagate its relevance. It concludes that contextualizing comparative education shows its extreme relevance in research and teaching, in order to contribute to comparative literature.

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CONTENT ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL REPRESENTATION IN THE NARRATIVES OF CHRONICALLY ILL PATIENTS

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the article analyzed: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the content expressed. This construction of discourse permeates the entire process of human communication and is developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the discourse emanating from the subject. Objective: To analyze the content of textual fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation. Methodology: Qualitative research. In order to treat the material, we opted for Bardin’s (1977) content analysis method, which analyses the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way, as described by Minayo (2000), who organizes it into three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the results obtained and interpretation under the reference of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009). Final Considerations: In the analysis of the study, we found two distinct processes in the discourse, confirming our hypothesis that the attitude is influenced by everyday experiences. The study shows objectification and anchoring, analyzed on the basis of TRS, which demonstrates the influential role of everyday experiences and the transformation of the subjective into objective through the hierarchization of responsibility for one’s reality.

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DISTANCE EDUCATION AND DIGITAL INCLUSION: CONTRIBUTIONS AND CHALLENGES

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the relationship between Distance Education (DE) and digital inclusion. The literature review revealed that distance learning provides access to education for different social groups, but digital inclusion is crucial. Limited internet access and a lack of digital skills were challenges identified. It was recommended to invest in connectivity infrastructure, digital training programs and electronic devices. In addition, addressing inequalities and promoting partnerships between educational and government institutions is key. The conclusion emphasizes the importance of digital inclusion for equal opportunities in distance learning, seeking an inclusive and equitable education. Overcoming the challenges identified will contribute to full student participation. In summary, this research highlights the need for targeted policies and strategies to promote digital inclusion in distance learning, with a view to the participation of all students.

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EDUCATION, A CONSTITUTIONAL AND SOCIAL RIGHT, IN PANDEMIC TIMES - A BRIEF DISCUSSION

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The Right to Education is a constitutional and social right, understood as a human right. Brazil has faced educational problems of inequality and equity in access to education for decades. Faced with the context of a pandemic and social isolation, education has become remote, highlighting the difficulties previously faced, making them emerge, which has fostered debates and discussions nationwide, in the three federal, state and municipal spheres. Thus, the study is justified because it is necessary to reflect on the right to education as a constitutional and social right, in times of pandemic, and aims to analyze the right to education in Brazil in the current post-pandemic moment. To this end, bibliographic research was used, carried out in a virtual environment, with articles made available and annals on reliable websites, notebooks and theses with scientific content that, as well as discussions and results, are presented in titles. The author's conclusions and some impressions can be found in the final considerations.

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EMPOWERING ATTITUDES IN THE FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Ableism is the specific prejudice against people with disabilities. Even after the implementation of various laws aimed at inclusion, it is still possible to see barriers that prevent people with disabilities from participating in society. Among these barriers is the attitudinal barrier, which is considered to be attitudes or behaviors that prevent or hinder the social participation of people with disabilities on equal terms. Many attitudinal barriers occur within the family environment, due to a lack of information. Empowerment in family relationships often manifests itself implicitly, in a protectionist way, when they consider their disabled family members to be incapable, developing words and actions that frustrate the development of their autonomy and when they disrespect their desires and emotions, taking away their right to respond to their wishes and desires, as if they had no will of their own, no voice and no turn to resolve situations in their lives. Society must learn to see people with disabilities as fellow human beings and not as inferior beings. And this learning must begin at home, including with the disabled person's family members, who tend to overprotect them.

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FROM TRAINING TO PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: A STUDY BASED ON THE SOCIAL PROJECT FOR PSYCHO- PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION (PROSIPP) DEVELOPED AT THE FRANCISCAN INSTITUTE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN PAÇO DO LUMIAR, MA

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The case study carried out at the Franciscan Higher Education Institute (IESF) deals with the relevance of psychopedagogy and continuing training for the psychopedagogues taking part in the Social Project for Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp).

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INCLUSION AND EQUITY: A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO HUMANIZED CARE FOR DEAF PATIENTS

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

It is known that one of the fundamental principles that brings dignity to human beings is communication. Through communication it is possible to guarantee rights, interaction and enable effective care. Communication becomes effective for deaf patients when the Brazilian Sign Language (Libras) is used. In this way, it is possible to ensure greater patient confidence in diagnoses and treatments, as well as promoting a holistic approach with equity and humanization in care.

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INNS IN CALDAS NOVAS (GO): MANAGEMENT AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE ENVIRONMENT FROM 2015 TO 2020

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the management and relationship with the environment, in the years 2015 to 2020, of hostels in Caldas Novas, a municipality in the state of Goiás, which has a very high economic development, driven by the growth of the state's large urban centers.

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MISTHANASIA: A PRACTICE RESULTING FROM THE STATE'S FAILURE TO GUARANTEE FUNDAMENTAL HUMAN RIGHTS

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

To present the inconsistencies in Brazil's health system, as well as the incoherence in the application of the Principle of the Reserve of the Possible, pointing out the need for judicial activism in order to rescue the dignity of living and also of dying.

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NEUROPLASTICITY & EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE - ALLIED TO THE COMMANDERS OF THE MILITARY FIRE DEPARTMENT / SOUTHERN REGION - GOIÁS

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

This study, through the capacity of cerebral neuroplasticity, allows us to increase the level of emotional intelligence in the actions of Military Fire Brigade commanders in their troops.

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SELF-DEFENSE AS AN EDUCATIONAL ACTION FOR INCLUSION

AUTHORS

Angel do Nascimento Siqueira; Luisa Fernanda Mendes Anversa; Simone Ribeiro Azevedo; Tutor: Valeria de Fatima Soares Marques Coelho (valeria_marques_65@hotmail.com)

ABSTRACT

Self advocacy refers to the ability of people with intellectual or multiple disabilities to express themselves, make their own decisions and defend their rights. It consists of a program that originated in the APAE Network in defense of valuing diversity and promoting the dignity of children, young adults and the elderly with intellectual and multiple disabilities. In this way, this study seeks to analyze self-defense as an educational action for inclusion. This research consists of a case study of an observational and documentary nature with a qualitative approach, in which the actions of self-defense carried out at APAE Niterói over the years with those assisted were observed. Documents were analyzed, including records of meetings of self-defenders and the researchers' field diary. Over the years, there has been a growth in the discussions and actions of the self-defense with great support from people with disabilities. However, it can be seen that the self-defenders' demands have remained almost the same over the years, as is the case with bullying in schools and discrimination. We conclude that although legislation seeks to reduce these gaps, very little concrete action has been taken by society to remedy them.

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SYSTEMATIZED BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW: GENERAL COMPETENCIES OF THE NURSE PRECEPTOR FOR THE PRACTICE OF UNDERGRADUATE CURRICULAR INTERNSHIP

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To identify in the literature the competencies of the nurse preceptor for monitoring the supervised curricular internship in undergraduate nursing. Methodology: Systematized bibliographic review analyzed in light of the national curricular guidelines for undergraduate nursing described in CNE/CES Resolution No. 3 of November 7, 2001. Results and discussions: 451 articles were retrieved, and one study was analyzed that was related to the competence of the preceptor in primary care, referenced in the DNC/ENF in the health care item. Conclusion: The different studies confirmed our initial hypothesis that the general competences are included in the profile of the graduate in nursing. The different studies used synonyms to describe the competences, which can lead to variations in interpretation.

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THE CHALLENGES OF VACCINATION IN THE STATE OF AMAZONAS

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ABSTRACT

The population of the interior of the state of Amazonas lacks basic health care and actions such as vaccination. Given this problem, what are the main challenges to be overcome in relation to vaccination in the state of Amazonas?

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THE EPISTEMOLOGY OF PRIVATE LAW

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this article is to propose a reflection on the epistemology of private law. When referring to epistemology in Law, it is important to look back at history, when records show that, for a long time, everything produced outside positivist Law, containing critical content, was considered not to be science. This was due to the positivist view that science was absolutely neutral (the myth of neutrality). All other knowledge would be included in the field of morality, politics and religion, except scientific knowledge. It is important to note that positivism is not the same thing as legal dogmatics, and for some it is more than a current of thought, reaching the status of an Epistemology. This is a bibliographical study in which various publications on Internet sites were used.

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THE IMPACTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES FOR ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

School physical education is characterized by classes made up of activities that involve various bodily practices and experiences. The place of bodily practices in the educational process is of the utmost importance, as they present yet another possibility for reading the world. Through body practices, young people can portray the world in which they live, produce and reproduce their values, beliefs, feelings, concepts and prejudices. Through bodily practices, young people and adolescents can construct their place of speech in cultural and social dynamics. The pandemic caused by Covid-19 has led physical education teachers to adapt their content to the new reality. Thus, in addition to the challenges present in face-to-face classes, the return to schools has also brought significant transformations in the educational sphere.

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THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CARDIAC SURGERY SERVICE IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF PARNAÍBA - PIAUÍ, BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

Changes in the profile of patients with structural heart disease have been observed in recent decades, reflecting the greater longevity of the general population and the increased severity of those referred for surgical treatment, making it necessary to offer specialized services in cardiovascular surgery. Objective: To analyze the process of implementing the cardiac surgery service in the municipality of Parnaíba. Methods: This is a documentary, intervention and retrospective study with a qualitative and quantitative approach. Results: The process of receiving patients eligible for cardiac surgery before the service was set up was identified; the implementation of the cardiac surgery service in the municipality of Parnaíba was inferred; the legacy of the implementation of the cardiac surgery service in the municipality of Parnaíba was identified, as well as the subsidies needed to draw up programs for technical and professional development and improvement. Conclusion: The final responsibility for the success or failure of the surgical patient's evolution lies primarily with the act. Although some unfavourable organizational factors are often beyond the scope of this procedure, these factors undoubtedly play an important role. In view of these peculiarities, there is a perennial need for everyone's involvement, especially with regard to monitoring surgical results, demanding better working conditions and investing in professional training and research applied to daily practice.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SUPPORT TEACHER FOR THE COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTISTIC STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY IN A STATE SCHOOL IN GOIATUBA, GOIÁS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to analyze whether students with Autism Spectrum Disorder have the ability to develop their cognitive skills in the school context and the importance of the Support Teacher in this process as a key element for learning to take place. Future work should be more comprehensive and address all students diagnosed with autism in state, municipal and private schools.

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THE METAVERSE IN EDUCATION: POSSIBILITIES AND CHALLENGES TODAY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, it has been possible to observe a major technological revolution. The COVID-19 pandemic has made information around the world even more accessible in the palm of our hands, a reality never seen before in history. The educational process has moved from blackboard and paper to online, signaling that a new reality would enter without revival. Talking about the Metaverse in Education not only instigates interest among some people in this subject, but can also point to possibilities and challenges for its implementation in the teaching and learning process.

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NEUROSCIENCE AND LITERACY: BRAIN PROCESSES AND EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study looked at the relationship between neuroscience and literacy, with the aim of understanding the brain processes involved in learning to read and write. Using a literature review approach, relevant studies published in the last ten years were selected. Analysis of the results revealed the importance of phonological skills, the dual pathway model and neural plasticity in this process. The results highlighted the need for teachers to be familiar with neuroscientific knowledge in order to improve their educational practices. Incorporating these contributions can improve academic performance and promote more effective pedagogical strategies in literacy.

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THE ROLE OF THE STUDENT UNION IN DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The research showed the potential of analyzing the role of the student union in engaging students in a culture of participation in pedagogical activities that can really contribute to democratic management and the learning process in everyday school life. The general aim of this research was to analyze the role of the student council in democratic management and its contributions to the learning process. The research used a qualitative approach and the extended case method with semi-structured interviews to capture data.

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THE USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS IN SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The pandemic we are experiencing has only accelerated the growth of technology in education. Teachers have been forced to develop skills with the most diverse digital tools in order to continue the teaching and learning process. Knowing the importance and compulsory nature of Physical Education in Brazilian basic education, this subject was, like all the others, adapted, where through ICT (information and communication technology) it was possible to promote and experience interactive, dynamic and practical classes as well. Every day was a new challenge to face, but this experience brought teachers learning and techno-scientific mastery. Even after returning to face-to-face classes, the technological tools became allies in the teaching-learning process, attracting students' attention and becoming another option to help physical education teachers in their practical and theoretical experience.

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WRITTEN LANGUAGE IN THE FACE OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES: ITS IMPACT AVA-MOODLE AT IFSUDESTEMG - SÃO JOÃO DEL REY - BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

With the popularization of the Internet, there has been an increase in the number of mobile devices and, as a result, the development of computer tools. The use of computational tools in virtual learning environments allows for numerous teaching-supported experiences. This work highlights pedagogical aspects in the development of teacher writing in a virtual learning environment - Moodle. It analyzes the use of information and communication technology (ICT) by teachers and students in virtual learning environments. It aims to identify teachers' writing through a quantitative and qualitative study to investigate the influence on students' writing patterns of the use of formal language to the detriment of digital language, "internetese", supported by the use of synchronous and asynchronous tools. The study proves that teenagers not only know how to distinguish which computer tool they are on, but also behave according to the formality of a forum or the informality of a chat.

THIRST

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